

CHARACTERISTICS OF BELLY WRESTLING IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: In Uzbekistan, it is forbidden to move the legs in relation to the opponent in wrestling: kicking, pressing the leg, hanging, kneeling, grabbing the legs, etc. In addition, it is not possible to remove the hand from the opponent's belt, knock down the opponent without lifting him, knock him down from the waist and knock him out of the mat. As a rule, it is customary to grab the opponent by the waist.

Key words: Wrestling, belt wrestling, opponent, mat, referee, exercise, solo, power, play, wrestler.

Characteristics of the rules of wrestling in Uzbekistan. In wrestling with a belt, you can move forward, backward or sideways when you hold and lift the opponent. [2:36]. As soon as you lift it from the ground, you need to quickly turn it, throw it back and forth, to the sides. A quick turn to the left or right is required during a takedown, which throws the opponent to the side or into a shovel. In belt wrestling, it is forbidden to move with the legs in relation to the opponent: hitting, pressing the leg, hanging, bending the knees, grabbing the legs, etc. In addition, it is not possible to remove the hand from the opponent's belt, knock down the opponent without lifting him, knock him down from the waist and knock him out of the mat. As a rule, it is customary to grab the opponent by the waist.[4:51] Then they hold the belt in the left hand in the same way. The referee asks both wrestlers if they are ready for the match and starts the match with a whistle. It is necessary to grab the belt, and it is impossible to release it during the takedown, and it is impossible to move with the legs until the opponent lifts his leg from the mat. According to the rules of belt wrestling, there are several methods of wrestling technique. The most used ones are lifting and throwing forward, spinning, throwing to the right and left, hook, lifting the opponent from the mat with a quick movement to the side, half bending and bending to the side. [2:76]. We bring to your attention a system of exercises for mastering the techniques used in fighting. Exercises are performed individually, in pairs, on a dummy, on a trainer with quarter strength, half strength, full strength, and defense against opponent methods. Before learning how to protect yourself from attacks and methods in exercises, it is necessary to practice methods in the form of "fighting with the shadow". For example: 1. "Shadow fighting" methods should be expressed without communication: forward, backward, left, right steps. It is necessary to measure steps in different widths, speed and rhythm (1 minute). 2. Change position (high, medium, low) and move in different directions, showing deceptive movements and catches (2 minutes). 3. Movements representing catching, tricking, off balance, moving with the feet, throwing, protecting from techniques. 4. Moving by means of unbalancing, knocking or throwing (without injuring the opponent) while grabbing the clothes. You can use any method you want in "Shadow Fighting".^[4] We offer the following exercises in order to thoroughly learn the

technique of playing from the back foot: 1. Participants stand in the position of the right foot. Grabbing your partner's clothes, shift your body weight to your right leg and pull it back to the left with a quick movement of both hands. Turning to the left, step the right foot in front of both of the partner's feet. Through the active movement of the hands, the push of the right leg and the left-forward movement of the body, the opponent falls to the mat. 2. The opponent resists (same as the previous task). It is required to perform the exercises in sequence. 3. Kicking the back leg when the opponent approaches, moving backwards and forwards at moderate speed. Exercise should be done with 1/4 strength. 4. Performing the exercise with half strength resistance. Do not forget about safety. 5. Doing the exercise with another partner.^[5] Later, you can step forward, backward, sideways with your feet, hold the opponent in a comfortable position with your hands, and perform the exercise of hitting him. Here are some special exercises with elements of martial arts to improve speed, agility, and coordination of your movements: 1. While standing on two legs, one leg, and kneeling, or standing on a gymnastic bench, put your palms on the opponent's palms and throw him off balance. 2. Standing on one or both legs, pull the opponent out of the line (take out). 3. Standing with the left leg forward, try to grab the opponent's shoulder. While standing on the left knee, join the fingers of the right hand (the thumb should look up) and try to grab the opponent. 4. Expressing distraction, hitting the opponent's left palm, thigh, elbow, head, shoulder, knee with a quick hand movement. 5. Pushing or lowering the opponent's hand to the side. 6. Turning the opponent back and grabbing (squeezing) the opponent's body or grabbing the body with one hand from the front. 7. Standing with his back at a distance of 1 step from the opponent, putting his hands on the side. Quickly lowering the hands when the opponent tries to grab the waist. 8. Pushing the opponent out of the circle with the body and hands. Jumping on one or both legs to push the opponent (palm to palm). 9. Taking the ball from the opponent's hand with one or two hands after the signal is given.^[6] This exercise can also be done with a gymnastic stick. Standing or sitting 1-2 meters away from the ball on the ground, be the first to pick it up when the signal is given. 10. Performing distracting actions in a circle with a diameter of 1.5 meters. The main task is to choose a favorable situation and grab the opponent's arm and belt. 11. Sitting on the side, hands on knees. Grabbing the opponent's waist with a signal (the opponent must turn left to the side). 12. Sitting with their backs to each other, putting their hands on their knees, turning according to the signal, grabbing the opponent by the neck (behind the head) with the right hand. It is necessary to protect with the left hand. 13. Lying close to each other (head turned to one side), when a signal is given, one person stands up, and the other tries to catch him. 14. When a sign is given while lying down, stand up quickly and grab the opponent's waist from behind or in front.^[7] He is attracting the attention of the whole world and is gaining popularity. The struggle that captivated millions has its deep historical roots as one of the highest spiritual values of the world. As a result of the researches, researches and archeological research conducted by historians and philosophers, the information found confirms that the age of the struggle is at least 2.5-3 thousand years old. Agile acrobats were popular among the peoples living in Central Asia in the IV century. Agile, highly trained goalkeepers travel to countries such as Greece, Byzantium, and Iran to perform their spectacular and dangerous games in a variety of circus scenes enriched with sharp satire and laughter by clowns and clowns, flying magicians, and incredible the games of the wrestlers, the lively dances of the wooden legs, and the deep meaning of the words and verses of the horse-plays, and the exercises adapted to these

games. This is evidenced by the unique finds, assoriatics, and rock art found in the oases of Surkhan, Zarafshan, and a number of ancient settlements of the Ferghana Valley. "There are 6 pieces of evidence that scientifically prove the history of our struggle. For example, the wall painting of two fighting wrestlers found in Panjikent is considered a unique monument of the Sugdiyana statehood, that is, the medieval period. One of such objects is a cylinder-shaped ceramic vessel. lib, it was found in the territory of ancient Bactria (South "Uzbekiston"). One of his pieces depicts two wrestlers and one of them kicking his opponent. In the figurines on the rim of another bowl, wrestlers are shown raising their arms and getting ready to fight. The objects found in Chelak village near Samarkand echo from the past. Among these dishes, a silver-plated package is especially noteworthy. On its handle, two wrestlers are fighting in the Uzbek wrestling style. This find belongs to the early Middle Ages. According to the studies of ethnographers, the oldest epics, fairy tales and legends also contain scenes about the fight. If you look closely at their content, you will see that they belong to the era of matriarchy. It follows that the history of Uzbek wrestling dates back to the 5,000-year-old era. There were three types of wrestling tradition among the Uzbek people. Its earliest appearance was as a physical exercise - in connection with the exogamous marriage ceremony. During the marriage ceremony, the future bride-groom's fight was organized by the ruling women of that time. This phenomenon arose due to the right of the matriarchal kingdom to try and choose the land. The physical evidence found as a result of the researches, researches and archeological scientific researches and observations carried out by historians, antiquarians, philosophers and scientists prove that the age of Kurash is at least 2.5-3 thousand years old. In the oases of Surkhan, Zarafshan and a number of ancient settlements of the Fergana valley the identified rare finds, assyriatics, examples of fine art carved into the rocks testify to this. "There are 6 findings and material evidence that scientifically prove the history of our wrestling. For example, the wall painting of two wrestling wrestlers found in Panjikent is considered a unique monument of the Sugdiyana statehood, that is, the medieval period. Wrestling in the territory of Uzbekistan dates back to IX-X AD. "It is widely developed in Asia, and it is traditional to hold competitions on folk festivals. The local population attached special importance to the celebration of various ceremonies, especially on Navruz days," writes S.P. Tolstov. The first three days of this holiday On this day, the parks where wrestling shows were organized under the leadership of the elders and elders of the country were filled with people. In this regard, the prisoners were freed from the sins of the criminals. It is important that the fights were a real training school for the representatives of the younger generation. "Alpomish", "Gorog'li", "Avazkhan", "Rustam", "Toganoy", "Kuntug'mish", which are examples of Uzbek folk art, glorify the struggle of wrestlers. dexterous and nimble intelligent and wise people are glorified. In the works of Muqaddasi, an Arab geographer and traveler who lived in the 10th century, Movorounnahiming Mavr. It is noted that wrestling matches were often held in big cities like Samarkand, Bukhara, Balkh. Benazir Allama Abu Ali ibn Sina (980-1037) also said, "It is no coincidence that in the book of medical laws, fighting is of special importance in the mental and physical condition of a person. According to the great doctor, those who are regularly engaged in physical education do not need to be cured of the disease. Works such as "Shahnoma", "Qabusnoma", "Zatarnoma", "Baburnama", "Abdutkanoma", which are considered to be masterpieces of Eastern literature, have a vivid outline of the poetry and appearance of the poets, and their spiritual world is reflected in bright-colored images. His Highness Alisher Navoi also attended the ceremony of wrestlers

who spread wrestling and its magic to seven climates. Therefore, in many works, he wrote down wonderful events and pictures about the life and work of wrestlers. In the special "Kholoti Palilavon Muhammad" manoq (biographical work) dedicated to the wrestlers, the great creator, the incomparable wrestler of his time, Pahlavan Muhammad, in addition to the art of wrestling, discussed religious and worldly sciences, including astronomy and mathematics, chemistry and philosophy, literary studies and perfectly acquired art studies, law studies and other knowledge. It is said that the poets of that time first showed their new works to him and took advice from Pahlavon Muhammad's fine understanding of poetry.^[8] Every young man or woman who wants to fully learn wrestling must thoroughly study its history, follow its rules, ethics and moral principles. He should never tarnish the reputation of his homeland and of course the struggle with his actions and morals, and he should remain loyal to his people, country, struggle in any case until the last minute of his life. In addition, wrestlers should not talk too much during training or training (if it is not necessary), concentrate on one place and not look at other things, not injure each other, when they are gathering to learn a technique. it is necessary for them to inform their partners immediately if there is any defect in each other's wrestling clothes.

One such object is a cylinder-shaped ceramic vessel, which was found in ancient Bactria (Southern Uzbekistan). In one of its parts, two wrestlers are depicted and one of them is kicking his opponent. In the figurines on the rim of another vessel, wrestlers are shown raising their arms and getting ready to fight. This dish belongs to the Bronze Age, and it testifies to the fact that the history of ukurash is even longer, that is, 3.5 thousand years.

References:

1. Kurash haiqaro qoidalari, texnikasi va taktikasi. K.Yusupov G'ofur G'ulom nomidagi nashriyot T. 2005 y.
2. Kurash A.Atayev T. «O'qituvchi» 1987 y.
3. Sultanov AI PUBLIC EDUCATION CHARACTERISTICS OF RULES OF WRESTLING SCIENTIFIC AND METHODOLOGICAL JOURNAL OF THE MINISTRY OF PUBLIC EDUCATION OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN 2021, No. 5 (special) 60-62 The history of our struggle and today's development. Teacher and continuous education
4. Sulstonov A.I. Formation of professional cultural relations in future physical education teachers (on the example of Kurash). School and life "Avloni – 2020 20-23 b.
5. Sulstonov A.I. Improving maneuvering skills in highly qualified judokas. UZMU NEWS, 2018, №1 / 2/1. 100-103 b. 9.
6. A.I.Sulstonov. Kurash turlari va uni o'qitish metodikasi.(Belbog'li kurash) Toshkent:2022
7. K.Yusupov. Kurash halqaro qoidalari texnikasi va taktikasi. Toshkent 2005.
8. R.S. Salomov. "Sport mashg'ulotlarining nazariy asoslari" O'zbekiston Davlat jismoniy madaniyat instituti Toshkent 2005 yil.238-bet 6. Goncharova O.V. Yosh sportchilarning jismoniy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish Toshkent., O'zbekiston Davlat jismoniy madaniyat instituti 2005 yil - 171 b. 7. Sulstonov A.I, Kurash turlari va uni o'qitish metodikasi.(Belbog'li kurash) Toshkent 2001